

Beyond the Rituals: a meta-reflexive perspective on game study events, with a case study of the 20th Annual Tampere University Game Research Lab Spring Seminar

Academic events perplex me. Like migratory birds, we flock to distant cities in a seasonal cycle, perching in projector-lit rooms to exchange esoteric twitters face-to-face. I digitally scribble semi-coherent notes between bouts of daydreaming and caffeine withdrawal. In the evenings, some of us gather in bars dimmed like aquariums, voices crescendoing in shared excitement or boredom or overstimulation.

I'm struck by the ritualistic nature of these events.

Why do we do it?

Surely, in an age of instant digital connection, there are more efficient ways to share ideas. Video calls eliminate the carbon costs of travel. Online repositories increase access to knowledge. Real-time collaborative platforms allow fluid development of concepts unbound by geography or schedule.

Yet the comforting cadences of conferences and the like endure. I suspect it is not despite but *because* of their inefficiencies that we cling to them. Rather like a religion, the continuity itself becomes the purpose, even when divorced from practical function. There is a nostalgic romance to these rituals that digital conveniences cannot replace.

But do these rituals enlighten or self-perpetuate?

Prominent keynotes can reinforce inflated egos. Deference to revered ancestors and texts can calcify dogma. The demands of travel, schedule, family, funding, and health inevitably exclude some voices. And the tedium of PowerPoint template after template numbs minds ... and backsides.

Clearly, the spontaneous chats in corridors, the shared embodiment of space, the serendipity of discovering a new thinker—these hold irreplaceable value. Yet, for me, these rituals call to be scrutinized.

A few years ago, beyond academic, I was drawn to *Death Stranding*—not to critique its gameplay but to probe its cultural imprint. My project META-STRAND analyzes the game through playful yet piercing fragments rather than systematic analysis. Openly publishing these speculative strands on a website epitomizes my spirit of intellectual wanderlust—charting unmapped terrain, embracing digressive detours, challenging academic norms and boundaries along the way.

This subversive instinct now compels me to train my gaze introspectively, meta-analytically on the very knowledge practices and rituals I myself—and we, scholarly fellows—perpetuate.

What we do when we *do academia*?

As a 10-minute provocation, I'll offer an insider analysis of our enactment of "serious" scholarly practices as they unfold in real-time at the 20th Annual Tampere University Game Research Lab Spring Seminar. I'll start by examining the initiation rituals of the call for papers, submission guidelines, and acceptance processes. What works become labeled as Spring-Seminar-worthy scholarship? Which approaches are favored or overlooked? I'll note patterns in demographics and schools of thought among accepted proposals to reveal trends in whose work gains access.

Next, I'll summarize data about us as participants—affiliations, roles, seniority— and compare this to overall submissions. This exposes which groups most prominently populate the gathering.

Finally, I'll review Q&A discussions, tallying theory vs. methodology questions and coding response types as validating, challenging, etc. This reveals our preoccupations and group dynamics beneath the surface preening.

By meta-reflecting on our own rituals-in-action, I aim to spark discourse on how norms of "proper" scholarship nurture or hinder multi-perspectivity and interdisciplinarity. My goal is to critically yet collegially explore possibility spaces within our knowledge culture.

My full paper will delve deeper, examining artifacts of academia—calls for papers, citations, conference proceedings—as sites of struggle over scholarly capital and discursive power. From the venerable halls of DiGRA or the Foundations of Digital Games to the emerging voices in queer and Black game studies or simply tracing 20 instants of materials from the Tampere Game Research Lab Spring Seminar, I seek to unearth the unspoken dynamics that shape the contours of knowledge. In this landscape, calls for papers become the gatekeepers of orthodoxy, the evolution of paper titles a map of intellectual trends, and citation networks the genealogy of academic power.

Ultimately, I aim to denaturalize academic events as neutral rituals of knowledge exchange or production. Rather, I'll resituate them as constructs reflecting norms that evolved over time, often unintentionally perpetuating certain exclusivities masked as excellence. I'll conclude by contemplating concrete innovations to nurture intellectual diversity, turning stale events into forums for vibrant, heterodox thinking.

By “studying up” our own practices, this attempt is as much as self-reflection as it is an academic pursuit, a mirror held up to our collective scholarly selves as practitioners of knowledge—probing the integrity of the structures we inhabit, and within society as a whole.

Yet, amidst, this subversive quest, I find myself yearning for something else, pondering that scholarly publications and presentations have become increasingly monological—reviews ancillary to the paper, comments subordinate to the talk. Too often, academic discourse resembles social media's hierarchical

cascade with original posts above and fragmented commentary below. What if, instead of monologues, we embraced dialogues?

Therefore, instead of an arms-length meta-analysis, I propose an alternative, namely horizontal engagement: I offer to respond, not just reflect, to a fellow scholar's work, crafting a full paper as an attempt of a dialogue rather than a monologue. Rather than ritualized peering from a distance, let's migrate closer and exchange perspectives in good faith "tête-à-tête." For it's in the rousing duet of diverse viewpoints that insight truly takes flight.

And now, in a deliberate sidestep, this discourse eschews the traditional cloak of references and bibliographies. Why? To challenge the hegemony of academic citation, to escape the gravitational pull of intellectual forebears. This is an invitation for the reader to engage with the ideas herein not as mere reflections of past wisdom, but as entities in their own right, open for exploration and debate.

Victoria Mummelthei, February 2, 2024. Abstract for the 20th Annual Tampere University Game Research Lab Spring Seminar 7-8 May 2024.